

Rethinking Academic Plagiarism: The Role of a Missing Standard Definition

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Abstract

Despite numerous attempts to define plagiarism, there is still no universally accepted definition. This study takes the absence of a standardized definition as an opportunity to ask about the functionality of this conceptual openness of plagiarism. With the help of a qualitative content analysis, which examines 123 documents, such as guidelines, scientific articles and retraction notices in relation to plagiarism, central topoi of plagiarism were identified. By shifting the focus to social discourse practices surrounding plagiarism, I find that plagiarism is a dynamic and evolving concept, shaped by technological, societal, and institutional changes, which makes it both negotiable and adaptable across different contexts. A conceptual openness can lead to ambiguities and misunderstandings, as there is no single definition of what exactly falls under the term, but – and this is what this article attempts to highlight – this openness also facilitates communication and cooperation between institutions and actors.

What is plagiarism?

Despite its importance in research integrity, plagiarism lacks a standard definition, both in academia and law ((Weber-Wulff 2014, 4); (Eaton 2021); (Howard 2000)). The definitions of what constitutes plagiarism, and which practices it encompasses vary depending on the organizational context. These three different definitions of plagiarism by The Office of Research Integrity (ORI), The University of Oxford and the academic publisher Elsevier illustrate this argument:

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“Plagiarism is the appropriation of another person’s ideas, processes, results, or words without giving appropriate credit” (Office of Science and Technology Policy²).

The University of Oxford defines plagiarism as “Presenting work or ideas from another source as your own, with or without consent of the original author, by incorporating it into your work without full acknowledgement. [...] Plagiarism can also include re-using your own work without citation. Under the regulations for examinations, intentional or reckless plagiarism is a disciplinary offence” (Oxford University³).

“One of the most common types of publication misconduct is plagiarism – when one author deliberately uses another's work without permission, credit, or acknowledgment. Plagiarism takes different forms, from literal copying to paraphrasing some else's work [...]” (Elsevier 2017, Ethics in Research and Publication. Factsheet. Plagiarism⁴).

Furthermore, in Germany, legal decisions in the context of plagiarism proceedings are based on the act of deception, which is carried out intentionally or at least with conditional intent. The intent to deceive serves as the legal anchor point for actions such as the revocation of doctoral degrees. Plagiarism is the object of the deceptive act. The act of deception constitutes the legal criterion for the withdrawal, not the plagiarism, but it proves the deception.

In her 2009 conference paper “‘We know it when we see it’ is not good enough”, which is still widely quoted today, Fishman discusses the problem of a lack of a definition of plagiarism and its consequences in more detail. In order to overcome this problem, Fishman proposes five core elements by which plagiarism can be recognized.

“Plagiarism occurs when someone

1. Uses words, ideas, or work products
2. Attributable to another identifiable person or source
3. Without attributing the work to the source from which it was obtained
4. In a situation in which there is a legitimate expectation of original authorship
5. In order to obtain some benefit, credit, or gain which need not be monetary”

(Fishman 2009, 5).

In 2024 – a full 15 years after the publication of this conference paper – the issue of identifying plagiarism and its core elements remains highly topical as well as controversial. It is by no means the case that the scientific community can agree on a description at the working level. Furthermore, recent technical developments, such as the widespread use of AI like ChatGPT or Perplexity, which are based on Large Language Models (LLM) – just to name two prominent models –, are increasingly challenging the question of how to recognize plagiarism (Eaton 2023). I take the absence of a standardized definition of plagiarism as the starting point for my empirical research and ask: *How is plagiarism defined, perceived and treated in the academic discourse?* To explore this research question, I adopt

² <https://ori.hhs.gov/content/chapter-2-research-misconduct-office-science-and-technology-policy>

³ <https://www.ox.ac.uk/students/academic/guidance/skills/plagiarism>

⁴ https://researcheracademy.elsevier.com/uploads/2018-02/2017_ETHICS_PLA02.pdf

an empirical approach, conducting a qualitative content analysis of 117 documents to examine how different academic authors and institutions describe and define plagiarism within the academic discourse.

Based on the explorative research findings, I would like to propose a new approach: instead of focusing on the lack of standardization as a problem, I would like to focus more on the conceptual openness of the plagiarism term and ask about its functional properties. With this approach I follow authors such as (Howard 2000), who pointed out that “this indefinable thing” (473) of plagiarism suggests that it might be about something far more complex than just an undefined term. The aim with this approach is to focus more on the social practices surrounding the concept of plagiarism. If there is no agreement on a single definition ((Weber-Wulff 2014); (Eaton 2021); (Howard 2000)), further questions could be raised such as a) whether there are at least consistent perspectives on the fundamental common dimensions of plagiarism that constitute plagiarism and b) if so, what does these common dimensions provide for those dealing with plagiarism?

To explore this approach further, I will begin this article with a theoretical chapter on what discourses tell us about reality (chapter 1), which will be followed with a description of the research method and data (chapter 2). In chapter 3, I will describe the empirical findings. In chapter 4, I will summarize and theorize the findings for the subsequent discussion. In the discussion (chapter 5), I will go into more detail about the functionality of an open concept of plagiarism. The article ends with a conclusion (chapter 6) and shows what we can learn from this change of perspective for dealing with plagiarism in the future.

What discourses tell you

To what extent is it worth looking into or at a discourse surrounding the concept of plagiarism? In order to answer this question, we must first look at the main features of discourse analysis and its concerns. (Foucault 1972), who is also referred to as “the eminent authority of discourse analysis” (Nonhoff 2017, 1), is inextricably linked to discourse analysis. For Foucault, knowledge is a construct that is both visible and communicated in discourses. A discourse therefore permanently reproduces truths and determines what is socially accepted as true or correct at a given time. Discourses are therefore never neutral, but always closely linked to power and power relations, because they determine which statements are considered “true” and which ways of thinking and schools of thought are regarded as legitimate. Discourse analysis can be employed to examine the boundaries of social phenomena as well as those of society itself: Who or what is currently included? Who or what is excluded, or no longer part of it? Discourse analysis is therefore a useful tool for determining the boundaries of an object/field/group, etc. As a method it has continued to evolve in recent decades, developed its own tradition and is used in various methodological schools such as critical discourse analysis (van Dijk 2015), conversation analysis (Maynard and Clayman 1995) and dispositive analysis ((Agamben 2017); (Foucault 1972)).

Applying a discourse analysis to the subject of "plagiarism" seems worthwhile because plagiarism does not have a fixed definition. Because of that, various actors and institutions need to discuss and agree on what is currently meant by the term, making a discourse analysis of the term plagiarism the most suitable approach to yield results. What are the "truths" and "limits" reproduced in the discourse? If there is no fixed definition of plagiarism, then the empirical question of what are currently central topoi (Wengeler 2003) - i.e. patterns of argumentation and articulations that are (constantly) repeated in the discourse and have virtually solidified into a commonplace - becomes important. What truths can be gleaned from the plagiarism discourse and what can the field of research integrity and the actors in it derive from it for themselves and their work? These questions are pursued empirically below. Before I present and discuss the findings of the discourse analysis I performed, I describe in

more detail in the next section which method I chose for the analysis and which data sources I used for it.

Research Methodology

In order to explore central topoi of plagiarism, a qualitative content analysis (Mayring 2000) was conducted, analyzing a variety of text sources, including research literature, guidelines, legal opinions, policy documents and revocation notices. The goal is to construct a comprehensive understanding of plagiarism that reflects the perspectives of various actors and institutions in science. To achieve this, I use a sampling approach inspired by Q-methodology, a research technique developed by William Stephenson in the 1930s. Q-methodology systematically explores how individuals perceive a particular topic by studying subjective viewpoints (Watts and Stenner 2012). A central object of the Q-methodology is the recording of a discourse landscape, which refers to the collection of as many statements, ideas or opinions as possible on a single topic that represent the entire spectrum of people's possible points of view. This approach of the Q-methodology helps to analyse differentiated viewpoint clusters (topoi) that exist within a discourse.

Accordingly, a broad selection of documents from the academic field was chosen for the analysis in order to obtain a heterogeneous data set that reflects the different dimensions on the topic of plagiarism. All documents were imported into the qualitative data analysis software QDA-Lite and systematically coded by two people to insure intercoder referentiality (Mayring 2000). The coding was carried out from August until November 2024. The period for all documents examined is limited to the last 10 years: 2024 – 2014, if not state otherwise. This is mainly for practical reasons in order to make the amount of data manageable for a qualitative analysis. A bibliographic analysis shows a significant increase in the literature on academic plagiarism, since the 2000s (see Figure 1). Therefore, despite the limitation to a period of 10 years, a relatively large amount of the discourse is covered.

Figure 1: Number of academic plagiarism-related articles. Publication figures based on OpenAlex⁵. Own graphical representation.

⁵ OpenAlex is a free, open platform that offers metadata on scientific works. For more information about its data visit: <https://help.openalex.org/hc/en-us/articles/24396686889751-About-us>

The final dataset includes the following sources:

1. **International research articles** from the OpenAlex-Database: The cleaned sample contains 65 international research articles where “plagiarism” appears in both the title and abstract. The search query combined terms such as “research misconduct”, “academic integrity”, “plagiarism”, and “scientific misconduct”. A qualitative preliminary screening was used to ensure that only research articles that actually contained plagiarism as a central point of discussion remained in the sample. This sample includes articles from the UK, India, South Korea, USA, Japan, Brazil, Ukraine, China, Bangladesh, Thailand, Check Republic, Indonesia, South Africa and Slovakia. Articles written in languages other than English were not included in the sample in order to improve linguistic comparability within this data subset.
2. **Legal opinions pieces** from legal experts: This sample comprises two documents, each ranging from 20 to 60 pages.
3. **Publisher policies** from five leading academic publishers: Elsevier, Springer Nature, Science, Taylor & Francis, and Wiley—collected in 2024.
4. **Retraction notices** related to plagiarism: Using the “retractiondatabase.org”, this sample includes all articles retracted in Germany due to plagiarism (as one of the reasons) as of July 24, 2024. A total of 33 articles were identified, with 9 having at least one available retraction notice.
5. **Research integrity guidelines**: Guidelines from the 10 largest universities in Germany, ranked by student enrolment and two guidelines from the German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)).

Overall, 117 documents on plagiarism were analysed and coded for this qualitative research study.

I will begin the presentation of the empirical findings with the core question underlying each topos (cluster) and explain in detail how these are discussed from the perspective of the authors and institutions. In a second step, I will summarize the topoi distilled from the documents as overarching statements. This two-step approach is adopted to ensure better comprehensibility for the reader.

Based on the procedure of qualitative content analysis (Mayring 2000), a single topos is the summarized result of all codes collected for this single category. A single code in turn represents the summary of many text fragments, which contain statements and viewpoints on a thematic aspect. The codes obtained through the content analysis are presented below in quotation marks and usually consist of one or two words. To illustrate the results in more detail, examples from the data are quoted and come with a case number (e.g., case #1, case #2, etc.) as well as a citation of the respective document.

Topos 1: The conceptual universe of plagiarism

The data reveals a wide range of terms associated with plagiarism and describing different forms of plagiarism. In the documents, all terms used to describe plagiarism were coded. In total, nearly 30 different descriptions (codes) were identified across the 117 documents, including "literal copying", "substantial copying", "minor copying", "copy and paste", "paraphrasing", "self-plagiarism" and "text-recycling", "auto-plagiarism", "clear plagiarism", "plagiarism of ideas", "patchwork plagiarism", "systematic plagiarism", "stealing words", "Bauernopferreferenzen" (in English: pawn sacrifice references), "translation plagiarism", "text overlap", "image overlap", "mosaic plagiarism" and more. Additionally, terms such as "ghostwriting", "salami slicing" and "reproducing content" were also sometimes mentioned in the documents and discussed as quasi-subtypes of plagiarism. Despite the various terms that authors and institutions use in the documents to describe plagiarism, one important core element of plagiarism could be identified: “using another person's work” (Amirbekov 2024, 3)

(case #6) ; (Sayeda 2024, 22) (case #12) “without giving appropriate credit” (Amirbekov 2024, 3) (case #6).

These descriptions not only feature different subtypes of plagiarism but also highlight a range of related issues on the periphery of the *plagiarism concourse*. These include, for example, phenomena such as ghost-writing and self-plagiarism (for a wider discussion see (Hagenström 2022) and “Text Recycling Research Project”⁶), both of which have been increasingly discussed in recent years. According to the data, self-plagiarism seems to be one of the most debatable forms of plagiarisms. In order to describe the phenomenon more precisely, a conceptual shift has taken place from self-plagiarism to the term text recycling. Particularly in the development and use of new terms such as text recycling, the historical contingency of the plagiarism concept becomes evident. Plagiarism has many facets, which is reflected in the use of various terms and descriptions, and the boundaries of the plagiarism concourse continue to evolve.

Topos 2: The violation of scientific norms

To describe plagiarism adequately, it is not enough to specify the act itself, such as “copying” or “paraphrasing”. It is also (still) necessary to explain why plagiarism is problematic and for whom. Interestingly, justifications for why plagiarism is harmful to science frequently appear in the examined documents. This is somewhat surprising, because plagiarism is at the core of many definitions of scientific misconduct and therefore routinely investigated and sanctioned. Why plagiarism, particularly in academic research articles, still seems to require explicit justification and explanation is open to speculation. This may be due to the fact that the term is not legally defined (Weber-Wulff 2014), or because they do not necessarily have serious consequences for research results compared to forms of misconduct such as falsification and fabrication.

However, these justifications provide valuable insights into the norms being articulated. In the opinion of the authors of these documents, which scientific principles are being violated by plagiarism? How does plagiarism harm the scientific system? The data highlights three main principles or imperatives that plagiarism fundamentally violates: the *principles of honesty, independence, and originality*. The principle of honesty is violated when a plagiarist falsely claims to have conducted independent work. Independence is breached when someone uses the work of others without proper attribution. And, originality is undermined because plagiarism often involves reproducing existing knowledge, thereby falsely presenting it as original.

In addition to these three principles, the sample also identifies other moral arguments explaining why plagiarism is harmful to science. These include consequences such as the *impairment of the search for truth*, particularly through violations of honesty and originality, the general *breach of scientific integrity and ethical standards* as well as the *infringement of intellectual property rights*.

Thus, plagiarism undermines essential and numerous principles of scientific work, making it a serious form of misconduct, regardless of discipline or national origin of documents.

Topos 3: Causes of plagiarism

The documents discuss a range of factors that can facilitate plagiarism. These factors span from technological advancements (e.g., “Internet and AI”) to individual traits of the author (motivation, character), systemic conditions within the academic sphere (e.g., “publish-or-perish-culture”,

⁶ <https://textrecycling.org/>

"predatory journals" and "paper mills"), and deficiencies in education and awareness (e.g., "lack of research skills and awareness").

Regarding the technological advancements, the invention of the internet and its role in simplifying the duplication of text are frequently highlighted, as well as the recent development of AI and AI-assisted text generation. As one document notes, "[t]his is mainly because of the easy availability of material on the internet that can be copied and pasted into another document" (Goneppanavar 2013, 256) (case #7). Both the invention of the internet and the emergence of AI are regarded as milestones in the recent history of plagiarism.

The "publish-or-perish culture" is another significant factor that is assumed to foster plagiarism. On the one hand, it creates a "mandatory necessity for increasing number of research publications for career advancement [which is also] contributing as a driving factor for plagiarism" (Goneppanavar 2013, 256) (case #7). This publication pressure, in turn, promotes the emergence of "predatory journals" and "paper mills". As one case notes, "[o]ne of the biggest trends in academia is the move away from online and copy/paste plagiarism and toward essay mills" (Ashish, Pandey Kumar, and Saini 2023, 1) (case #2). A comprehensive exploitation mechanism has thus developed, with plagiarism at its core, even if it no longer appears predominantly in its original form as simple copy-and-paste. Plagiarism now represents a complex phenomenon that has acquired new layers of intricacy through the advent of the internet, AI, and exploitation mechanisms such as paper mills.

Further frequently discussed categories are "unintentional plagiarism" and plagiarism due to "cultural differences". Unintentional plagiarism happens, when sentences in one source match with sentences of another source, "[...] without the author actually plagiarizing them. It is also possible that [an] author might have read something previously [that] might exert an influence on him during the process of writing, with resultant similar sounding sentences, although he did not actually plagiarize" (Goneppanavar 2013, 256) (case #7). Plagiarism arising from cultural differences means that there are different understandings of plagiarism as well as intellectual properties, "which can [also] lead to unintentional plagiarism (Hayes and Introna (2005))" (Amirbekov 2024, 9) (case #6).

These perspectives on plagiarism highlight the complexity of plagiarism, where intent and context play significant roles in defining and evaluating such acts of scientific fraud.

Topos 4: Detection and prevention of plagiarism

Just as the causes of plagiarism vary, so do the measures proposed to prevent it. One of the most frequently mentioned detection strategies is the use of plagiarism detection software⁷, which plays a particularly central role in higher education. Examples include "checking for plagiarism by the best possible professional software available" (Debnath 2017, 1377) (case #1) or using "a sophisticated software for detecting plagiarized content in academic submissions" (Amirbekov 2024, 11) (case #6). A variety of tools used to detect plagiarism are named in the data: "Plagiarism Detection Software: Use tools like Turnitin, Grammarly, or Copyscape to detect potential plagiarism in written work" (Amirbekov 2024, 13) (case #6).

However, plagiarism detection software is not merely a tool for identifying and uncovering plagiarism; it also serves a preventive function. The use of plagiarism detection software is discussed as a preventive measure that operates based on anticipation and sanction, and it can therefore be regarded as a passive preventive measure: "[W]arning students by giving sanctions for those who commit plagiarism" (Hasanah and Harpeni Dewantara 2019, 38) (case #4). Plagiarism detection software assists

⁷ The correct wording would be "text similarity software", but I am referring to the wording in the documents and therefore use the term "plagiarism detection software" in this article.

primarily in identify potential instances of text similarity, raising red flags for further investigation. This mechanism inherently works within a framework of anticipation—it assumes that violations might occur and seeks to pre-emptively detect them. At the same time, its effectiveness is strongly tied to the sanctioning processes that follow (e.g., deregistration of the student, fail(ing?) the course). It also does not address the root causes or provide educational interventions. The use of detection software is often not accompanied by explanations of how flagged "matches" come about or what constitutes plagiarism in broader terms.

In contrast, more active measures such as “writing and citation courses” and efforts to “increase awareness” take a preventative approach. As one case suggests, these aim to “educate students and professionals about what constitutes plagiarism and why it is a serious issue” (Amirbekov 2024, 12) (case #6). The goal of such measures is to teach students and researchers proper citation practices, helping to prevent unintentional plagiarism and fostering an understanding of what plagiarism entails. Moreover, they emphasize strategies to actively avoid plagiarism during the writing process, thus addressing both knowledge gaps and behavioural aspects in a more holistic manner.

Another frequently mentioned set of measures includes the introduction of "plagiarism policies", "codes of conduct" and the establishment of a "new culture of integrity". These initiatives aim to promote a broader focus on the fundamental values of science, emphasizing the importance of upholding these principles across the academic community. By fostering an environment where ethical behaviour and adherence to scientific norms are prioritized, these measures seek to create a sustained cultural shift that strengthens the integrity of research practices.

Topos 5: Sanctioning of plagiarism

In addition to the definition of plagiarism, the category of sanctioning represents the second largest category within the coding system (n= 16 codes). This topos is therefore one in which there is the least agreement on the topic under discussion. The documents discuss a wide range of sanctions, from institutional to legal measures. These sanctions differ not only in terms of their formal severity but also with regard to the executing institution. For example, the sanction of "retraction" is a frequently discussed measure, primarily implemented within the realm of academic publishing. “Withdrawal of Published Work: If plagiarism is discovered in published work, the piece may be retracted, which can have lasting negative effects on an individual's professional standing” (Amirbekov 2024, 11) (case #6). Retraction watch, for example, is a platform on which retractions of scientific papers can be tracked.

Similarly, the "Corrigendum" or "Erratum" points in a similar direction, as the article is not retracted in this case; instead, the section in question is subsequently corrected. “When plagiarism is discovered post publication, the original publication will be corrected” (Patel 2023, 211) (case #5). Even though these sanctions may have reputation-damaging effects, the consequences of labour and civil law sanctions are considerably more severe. “The institution may take disciplinary action against the authors” (Goneppanavar 2013, 256) (case #7). “In matters related to copyright infringement, the publishers might pursue legal actions against the culprits” (Goneppanavar 2013, 257) (case #7). “Plagiarism brings about a wide range of consequences from academic penalties such as failing grades to legal repercussions in professional contexts” (Sayeda 2024, 22) (case #12). “If the plagiarized content is copyrighted, the original author may take legal action against the plagiarist, which can result in fines or other legal penalties” (Amirbekov 2024, 10) (case #6). Labour and civil law sanctions can, in some cases, result in the “exclusion from institutions, positions, and career opportunities,” which makes their consequences particularly significant. “In cases of severe or repeated plagiarism, a student may be suspended or expelled from their educational institution” (Amirbekov 2024, 10) (case #6). “Plagiarism can lead to termination of employment, especially in academic, research, and writing-related fields, and can hinder future job prospects” (Amirbekov 2024, 10) (case #6).

One of the sanctioning measures that is being actively debated – especially in Germany – is the "reprimand". A reprimand is generally considered a milder sanction and is often used when the misconduct is not deemed severe or intentional and it typically involves a documented warning that highlights the violation, emphasizes its unacceptability, and often includes recommendations for future compliance with academic integrity standards. While it aims to correct behaviour and uphold ethical norms, its effectiveness depends on institutional transparency and the perception of its adequacy as a deterrent within the academic community.

The five topoi of plagiarism

How is plagiarism conceptualized in the discourse? In this chapter, I provide a summary of the text analysis results and present them in a cross-sectional outline.

- a) **Plagiarism is not an inherent or fixed entity.** As a concept, plagiarism has at least three dimensions that determine the nature of plagiarism: a) a temporal, b) a contextual and c) an actorial one. The characteristics of plagiarism are historically contingent and, therefore, subject to change. This can be seen, for example, in the constant reinterpretation of the term. Moreover, the attributes ascribed to plagiarism vary depending on the domain in which it is discussed—be it university policies, research articles or legal expert opinions — and on the perspective of the actor, such as a university or a publisher, engaging with the concept. While a core definition of plagiarism often crystallizes around "the appropriation of content without proper attribution," its nuances (or the boundaries of the plagiarism discourse) remain fluid and adaptable.
- b) **Plagiarism is based on various normative imperatives.** By committing plagiarism, various moral and ethical rules in science are violated; among others, the principles of honesty, independence, and originality. Plagiarism thus undermines the integrity and credibility of the academic system as a whole. Plagiarism is clearly assigned to a social boundary area in which it represents undesirable social action. It constitutes an undesirable action because the consequences of plagiarism have a negative impact on academic integrity and the academic recognition system. In the discourse, a constant link is established between "knowledge production" and "authorship". It is this link that gives plagiarism its negative component. Without authorship, plagiarism is merely a repetition of what has already been said and/or a recomposition of what already exists. The correct attribution of authorship thus becomes a central category when it comes to the social constitution of plagiarism.
- c) **The roots of plagiarism are multi-factorial.** Systemic (pressure to publish), technical (internet, AI) and personal characteristics (motivation) are causes of plagiarism. Moreover, plagiarism carries a significant cultural dimension; perceptions of what constitutes plagiarism and how it is judged can differ widely across national and institutional contexts, reflecting varying norms, values, and educational practices. Science is a global phenomenon. Although standards determine national practices in dealing with knowledge and knowledge production, they are not self-contained. Science takes place on an international level, which also affects the field of scientific integrity. Different social and cultural values come together, and these then shape the plagiarism discourse. It can be seen that Western moral concepts about plagiarism are partly adopted in the international discourse and processed. This ignores the fact that also cultures exist in which "plagiarism" is a form of recognition and respect.
- d) **Detecting and preventing plagiarism focuses on technological tools,** education, and cultural initiatives. Plagiarism detection software, such as Turnitin or Grammarly are widely-used tools, particularly in higher education institutions. While primarily designed to identify text similarities, these tools also serve as a passive preventive measure by creating a system of anticipation and sanction. However, they often fall short in addressing root causes of

plagiarism, as they focus on flagging issues rather than educating users about proper citation practices or clarifying what constitutes plagiarism. More active prevention strategies focus on teaching proper writing and citation techniques through courses and awareness campaigns.

- e) **The sanctioning of plagiarism is multifaceted** and involves different actors such as courts, universities, publishers as well as different areas of society such as science, politics, and ethics. Accordingly, the scope of sanctions varies greatly. Relatively severe penalties such as the withdrawal of doctorates or consequences under employment law have a greater impact on a person's career than anonymized reprimands.

Discussion

The findings underscore that plagiarism is not a fixed concept but a dynamic issue that evolves over time and across contexts – which causes its discursive consistency. Despite the fact that the definition of plagiarism and the associated terminology shift according to technological advancements, societal norms, and institutional practices, there are common dimensions of plagiarism that are addressed across various actors and institutions: *its normativity, its complexity and its changeability*. Plagiarism and the associated violation of academic norms is a contemporary phenomenon that is constantly being updated against the backdrop of current societal developments. Science is not a closed space but is influenced by social and technologic developments such as digitalization, globalization, politics, big data and many more. A concept of plagiarism that is constantly reviewed in terms of its "core aspects" can also be seen as a constant evaluation: Under the current circumstances, does the term still fit the observable object? There are already voices that see the beginning of a "post-plagiarism era" (Eaton 2023), as technological developments such as artificial intelligence have (partially) made plagiarism in its original form superfluous. Whether we are really heading towards such an era remains to be seen. However, the discussions point to a constant re-examination of the fit of the term.

I argue that it is exactly this adaptability of the term that makes plagiarism negotiable for various actors and institutions. The empirical constitution of the term plagiarism is strongly reminiscent of the concept of the so-called "umbrella term" developed by (Rip and Voß 2013). Umbrella terms are terms that summarize a broad, often heterogeneous set of concepts, practices or phenomena. Such terms serve to unite disparate elements under a common linguistic or conceptual unit, even if these elements are not necessarily clearly defined or closely related. Umbrella terms are often used in interdisciplinary or emerging scientific fields to focus discursive attention, mobilize resources and promote a common agenda. Further examples of such terms are "sustainability", "innovation" or "(medical) translation". In some cases, they can be kept (deliberately) vague in order to include different actors and perspectives. This facilitates discursive communication and cooperation between institutions and stakeholders, but can also lead to ambiguities or misunderstandings, as there is not always a uniform definition of what exactly falls under the term. "Plagiarism" can be seen as an umbrella term, as it encompasses a variety of behaviours and concepts that may be very different but are summarized by a single term. At the same time, it can be observed that a wide variety of actors and entities – both within and outside the academic context – are concerned with plagiarism and contribute to its understanding. Conceptual openness is therefore highly relevant for the discussion of the phenomenon within academia and the scientific integrity community in particular.

If we revisit the problem of the lack of a standardized definition of plagiarism described in the introduction and approach this topic through the lens of the reorientation discussed here, what do we gain from it? By "we" I mean all the people who are entrusted with assessing plagiarism in their everyday professional lives. We gain assessment skills. The "We know it when we see it" (Fishman 2009, 5) is not necessarily to be understood as a failure of a system, but is possibly based on the critical judgment skills of actors who deal practically with the question of what plagiarism is and what

distinguishes it in their everyday lives. After all, there is no such thing as “one plagiarism”. There are various practices, motives, pieces of evidence, clues, etc. that indicate plagiarism (or not) and which have to be put together as a puzzle and assessed by professional actors in order to arrive at a viable decision. Doing this requires experience, critical assessment skills and constant training in the form of courses and further education. There are technical aids, such as text comparison software, but these also (still) require the critical perspective of (human) experts. It remains unclear whether plagiarism will ever be clearly defined, which does not mean that this cannot continue to be the desired goal. However, I would like to use this change of perspective to draw attention to the fact that - as long as this clear definition does not exist - we look at the actors who (have to) make this assessment in the context of such uncertainties and give them credit. We see it, because we know it. This, too, is a valid way of understanding the issue.

The investigation of the plagiarism discourse thus reveals two things: Firstly, the power of the concept of plagiarism lies in its openness. This is the only way to ensure permanent (re)evaluation and to constantly adapt the term to current practical needs. This appears to be of enormous importance, especially with the rapid socio-technical developments (such as internet and Large Language Models). Secondly, the evaluation of plagiarism and what is meant by it requires a constant critical perspective. This can only be guaranteed by actors with the appropriate training. Technical tools are not a critical evaluation authority. They can only provide indications that initiate, confirm and falsify an initial suspicion.

Conclusion

Plagiarism remains a concept without a standardized definition, varying across academic, organizational, and legal contexts. Definitions from institutions such as the Office of Research Integrity, the University of Oxford, and Elsevier highlight differing emphases to define plagiarism. Despite efforts like (Fishman 2009) widely cited framework proposing five core elements of plagiarism, consensus within the academic integrity community remains elusive, further challenged by technological developments such as the increasing use of Large Language Models (Eaton 2023).

This research article started with the premise that the absence of a standardized definition is not only a limitation but an opportunity to explore the functional properties of the conceptual openness of plagiarism. Using a qualitative content analysis, the study examined how plagiarism is defined, understood and addressed within the academic discourse. By shifting the focus from the lack of standardization of the term to the social practices surrounding plagiarism, I found a) consistent core elements—such as causes, norms, and sanctions—that inform its treatment and b) that plagiarism is a dynamic and evolving concept, shaped by technological, societal, and institutional changes, which makes it both negotiable and adaptable across different contexts, institutions, and actors. This adaptability aligns with the idea of an umbrella term as described by (Rip and Voß 2013), which unites diverse practices and phenomena under a single term, fostering communication and collaboration among various actors and institutions while retaining conceptual openness. While this flexibility enables a broad understanding, it also underlines the challenge of finding a uniform definition of plagiarism. Plagiarism is a complex case, the definition of which can only be negotiated through intensive exchange between different actors. The lack of a clear definition shifts the focus to the judgment of those tasked with evaluating plagiarism cases, such as (trained) research ombudspersons. Their ability to recognize and interpret the nuances of plagiarism is based on critical judgment, practical experience, and ongoing training. Recognizing the expertise of these individuals is crucial, as their assessment skills fill the gaps created by the absence of a definitive standard: We see it, because we know it.

My research attempts to better understand scientific plagiarism as a phenomenon and how it is dealt with. It does not stand alone, but joins an existing virulent discourse (see among others (Higgins, Lin, and Evans 2016); Fishman 2009; (Eaton 2023); (Howard and Davies Laura J. 2009); (Jereb et al. 2018); (Weber-Wulff 2014)). I hope my findings provide a new perspective and complement these debates in a fruitful way and create a new perspective on plagiarism.

Recommendations for practice

The results of the study make clear that the education and training of people who are entrusted with the assessment of scientific plagiarism in their everyday work (such as research ombudspersons and investigation committees at universities) must be more focused and that training based on minimum standards is needed. The field of scientific plagiarism in particular is so complex that assessment should be accompanied by appropriate training.

Limits of the empirical work

Even though attention was paid to the heterogeneity of the sample, this empirical analysis, like any other, has its limitations. This includes, for example, the fact that the qualitative study only looks at a section of reality. It is therefore not possible to make broader, generally valid statements, as is the case with standardized large-scale surveys, for example. Secondly, the discursive observation period is limited to 10 years. This means that developments that occurred prior to this are not included in depth, nor can any assessments be derived for the actual future.

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Disclaimer

For language optimization, I used DeepL and ChatGPT.